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LESSONS LEARNED? ONLINE-TEACHING DURING THE COVID 19 - PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The article presents our experiences switching from face-to-face to online-teaching during the first lockdown of the Covid-19 pandemic and the five essential core elements we used for our online-teaching. These are in detail: 1. Short lecture videos with essential explanations of the technical content, 2. More detailed exercise videos to deepen the technical content by means of various practical examples, 3. Interactive quizzes in the exercise videos to activate learners and to promote their understanding, 4. Weekly homework to encourage students to come to terms with what they have learned, 5. Consultation hours in a synchronous format to support student's learning process.

The article shows the way we went to create our learning format and the tools we used. Our considerations are supported by exemplary quotes from student feedback, both from the official assessment and from personal emails. Thanks to trustworthy communication with the students, we were always motivated to further develop our online-teaching. Finally, recommendations are given to stay in contact with the students and thus continuously develop the lessons.

1 INTRODUCTION

A good year ago, the corona pandemic paralyzed all university teaching. Within a few weeks, we teachers were forced to switch teaching from face-to-face to online teaching. A situation that had never been seen before and made us fearful that we would have to give up our teaching methods, which had been painstakingly worked

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up didactically over the years, with a focus on application-oriented learning [1] and promoting the understanding with demonstration experiments. Difficult decisions had to be made, which often represented a compromise between desirable and feasible in the short term. We want to present our path through the first two semesters of online teaching and the steps we learned here.

2 DEVELOPING THE ONLINE-TEACHING

2.1 Decisions and first steps

When it comes to online-teaching, you can choose between synchronous and asynchronous teaching formats. Both have advantages and disadvantages, so synchronous formats allow the learners a direct exchange with the lecturer and thus direct queries, on the other hand it is sometimes more difficult for the students, unlike in presence in the lecture hall, to concentrate alone in front of the screen. Not to mention distractions from family members or roommates on both sides of the connection. Furthermore, an unstable internet connection can lead to difficulties for both the teacher and the student. An asynchronous format allows students to learn better at their own pace. The materials provided, such as videos, can be stopped or rewound at any time if something needs to be repeated or if the learner first wants to recapitulate in an individual way what has just been explained, be it through research on the Internet or parallel processing of arithmetic problems. Weighing up these points, we decided on an asynchronous format, which beside allows students to watch the lecture to their preferred learning time. Not least because we feared that the server performance in the home network would not be able to withstand a lecture with around 400 connected students.

Before that, the event consisted of twelve to thirteen 90-minute lectures and six to seven in-depth exercises lasting around 180 minutes, each dealing with two lecture topics. It does not seem sensible or expedient to bring this one-to-one into a video format. While derivations and sketches were carefully built up on the blackboard step by step during the lecture and some practical anecdotes were told in order to keep the students' attention, we now decided to reduce the lecture videos to a maximum of 30 minutes. These should first of all present the essential formulas and explanations of the technical content and thus lay a first basis for the students to deal with the content. For this purpose, the students were provided with the content as well as an overview of questions as PDF files in order to solve them step-by-step with the lecture videos and thus to acquire content self-sufficient [2].

Detailed exercise videos should then deepen the students' understanding of the technical content and stimulate their interest through a variety of practical examples from everyday life and technology. In addition, the application of the formulas should be shown step-by-step through calculation examples.

In order to produce really appealing videos that support the students' learning, we orientated ourselves to the principles for effective educational videos (for example Signaling, Segmenting, Weeding, Matching modality) [2] and the cognitive theory of multimedia learning [3], but of course we could not implement everything perfectly in

the first step. First, the existing presentations had to be reprocessed: on the one hand reduced, on the other hand restructured and supplemented with new, easily understandable graphics, images and animations. Internet sources and references for in-depth discussion as well as short sample videos were researched and integrated. A whole team of student assistants was involved in the research and graphic design.

Next, the audio track was added to the finished presentations in PowerPoint [4]. It turned out that the most expensive microphone is not necessarily the best at the same time, you should plan enough time and choose both the room and the time of day well to avoid excessive background noise. The audio-visual presentations were finally converted into a video format. What is described here in a few words took a lot of time and revision loops. In the exercise videos, it was ensured that explanations alternate with practical examples and calculation examples of specific applications in order to get the students' attention in these longer videos (50-75 minutes). For this purpose, it also seems advisable to evoke a change of speaker, so another person spoke the calculation examples. Student assistants were instructed for this. In addition, the students were asked during the video from time to time to stop this in order to first perform the calculation themselves or to solve a question on their own.

The videos as lectures and exercises were made available to the students weekly in the online course on the ISIS website (<https://isis.tu-berlin.de>) of the Technical University of Berlin (Fig. 1.). Furthermore, as already mentioned, there was the content as PDF files and a further presentation with quiz questions on the topics.

In order to encourage the students to deal with what they have learned, weekly homework had to be done. These were included as tests in the online course. The tasks were available to the students for one week with an unlimited number of attempts. The aim was not to create additional pressure to perform, but actually to create a more in-depth discussion. Therefore, it was always possible to ask questions to one another and to the teachers in the consultation hours and in the exchange forum on the course page. The consultation hours were given in a synchronous format in a virtual meeting room on the course website (meet@ISIS).

2.2 Further developments in the next run

After the first online semester, we wanted to further develop the material for the next round, knowing that the corona pandemic will not allow us to return to regular teaching so soon. The lecture-free time was used to attend an online course "Screencast Masterclass - develop your own videos" [5] and to watch some tutorials [6] on the use of digital instruments, and to become familiar with them.

Now the videos were first revised with Camtasia. The volume was regulated, noises and many "ums" cut out and long pauses in speech shortened. The program also made it easier to integrate and shorten videos for demonstration examples. Furthermore, transitions were used and instructions for students were displayed in the video, such as "Please stop the video now and try to solve the arithmetic problem yourself first! "

In this program, a short personal welcome video was also created with a few tips for the students on how to use the learning videos (Fig.2.). So that the students not only see the lecturer as a picture, but actually personally from the home office, apart from the consultation hours, which were not visited by all students.

Fig. 1. Learning material provided weekly during the first online semester

Fig.2. Welcome video with five tips for using the learning videos and materials

Another important revision step became possible when H5P [5] content could be integrated into the online course. Now the learning videos could be enriched with different question formats, such as multiple choice (Fig.3.), single choice or fill in the blank questions, and links to further information in H5P in order to actually support active learning [6].

Fig. 3. Multiple choice question in the interactive H5P video

In addition, the consultation hours have been expanded in the second online semester, as well as communication via an exchange forum in the online course in order to stay in contact with the students and to be able to support them in the event of problems.

3 STUDENT FEEDBACK AND ONLINE EXAM

That our efforts bore fruit could not only be read in the official evaluation. We were particularly pleased about the unsolicited feedback from the students, which we received by email, a few examples:

“Good morning, I just wanted to say how well you are doing the exercises. The interest in the topics on your part and the intention to teach us students something can be seen in every single exercise. Thanks.” (student email 15.01.2021, 10:52)

“So with this in mind, a silent compliment to your commitment, your preparation and your constant help (and maybe also patience ..) in the forum. Many students will certainly appreciate that too.” (from a student email 03.02.2021, 10:24)

“Everything about the topics is very good to understand! The homework serves to practice the topics, the questionnaire helps you to remember the important aspects. Everything great.” (from the official evaluation WS2021_032)

Of course there were also some points of criticism, for example it was noted that the arithmetic tasks should be calculated in more detail (*“Maybe expand the arithmetic problems better, sometimes found it too fast.” (from the official evaluation WS2021_032)*). For this reason, we are currently in the process of completely processing the calculation tasks in the exercise videos as detailed step-by-step instructions.

In addition, we have set up a group division and a group forum in the online course to make it easier for students to find learning groups and exchange ideas. And we're still improving our online exam format [8]. After the first exam, which some students found to be too short in time (*“Like many others, I found the exam far too tight and at the end of the day I was unable to enter many of my results.” (student comment in the course forum 05.02.2021, 12:37)*) and too high in terms of level, we have already implemented some feedback from the students: such as enabling calculation paths to be uploaded directly after the exam, no fixed navigation, restructuring of the exam to make it easier to manage the time and clearer distribution of points for different levels of difficulty. Nevertheless, it remains a great challenge to test competency-oriented via an online format!

4 SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATION

Any tool is only as good as the hand that guides it. Regardless of whether you opt for synchronous or asynchronous learning formats, each format has advantages as well as disadvantages for learners as for teachers and the decision must be weighed personally. It is then more important to implement the learning format in an activating and supportive manner for the students. We opted for asynchronous online-teaching with the essential elements: short lecture videos as a basis, detailed exercise videos with calculation examples, interactive quiz questions and weekly homework.

If the learning materials are offered asynchronously, opportunities should also be created for students to ask questions and receive feedback on their learning pathways. This is another core element of our online teaching.

On the other hand, close contact with the students enables you to get to know their needs and thus to further develop your online teaching. In addition to synchronous consultation hours, we also recommend active participation in a discussion forum for your course. We also recommend lively exchange among colleagues about online tools in teaching and attending appropriate workshops, as that helped us a lot.

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